

***JUSTICIA CARNAE* HOOKER BUT NOT *FICUS CAPENSIS* PROTECTS AGAINST
MERCURY-INDUCED TOXICITY**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Mercury is a toxic environmental heavy metal that induces oxidative stress and hematological abnormalities. *Justicia carnea* and *Ficus capensis* are traditionally used in Nigeria as blood tonics, but their protective effects against mercury toxicity are undocumented. This study investigated the efficacy of *Justicia carnea* and *Ficus capensis* leaf extracts in mitigating mercury-induced toxicity in Wistar rats.

Materials and Methods: Thirty male Wistar rats were randomly assigned to six groups (n=5): control, mercury alone (1/10th LD₅₀), mercury with low (400 mg/kg) or high (800 mg/kg) doses of *Justicia carnea* extract, and mercury with low or high doses of *Ficus capensis* extract. Ethanol extracts were administered orally for 28 days. Blood samples were collected via cardiac puncture to assess hematological parameters (RBC, PCV, Hb, WBC, PLT), antioxidant biomarkers (glutathione, superoxide dismutase, catalase), oxidative stress marker (malondialdehyde), and hemostatic parameters (bleeding and clotting times). Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Tukey's post-hoc test (p<0.05).

Results: Mercury exposure significantly reduced RBC ($6.79 \pm 0.27 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$), PCV (41.88±6.05%), Hb (11.60±1.64 g/dL), and PLT ($971.40 \pm 45.48 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$), and increased WBC ($9.66 \pm 0.64 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) and malondialdehyde ($4.57 \pm 0.65 \mu\text{mol/L}$) compared to control (p<0.05). *Justicia carnea* (400 mg/kg) significantly improved RBC ($6.96 \pm 0.11 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$), PCV (43.06±2.70%), Hb (11.56±0.48 g/dL), and antioxidant levels, and reduced malondialdehyde ($3.15 \pm 1.08 \mu\text{mol/L}$) and bleeding/clotting times (p<0.05). *Ficus capensis* showed no significant protective effects.

Conclusion: *Justicia carnea* leaf extract effectively mitigates mercury-induced hematological and oxidative damage, supporting its use as a blood tonic. *Ficus capensis* lacks protective effects, warranting further investigation.

Keywords: Mercury, *Justicia carnea*, *Ficus capensis*, Oxidative Stress, Hematological Parameters, Antioxidants, Wistar Rats, Anemia, Phytochemicals, Toxicity

INTRODUCTION

Mercury is a pervasive environmental toxicant released through both natural and anthropogenic activities, such as silver and gold mining, coal combustion, dental amalgams, and dietary sources like fish [1-2]. Its high toxicity affects various life forms, including fish, birds, mammals, and humans, by disrupting cellular functions through altering protein structures and membrane permeability due to its affinity for sulfhydryl and selenohydryl groups [3, 2].

Environmental mercury exposure induces oxidative stress, depleting glutathione (GSH) and increasing reactive oxygen species (ROS), which can impair physiological and biochemical processes [4-5]. This oxidative stress is implicated in numerous human health conditions, including neurodegenerative disorders (e.g., Alzheimer's, Parkinson's), developmental disorders (e.g., autism, ADHD), cardiovascular diseases, and hematological abnormalities like anemia, lymphocytosis, basophilia, and neutrophilia [6-9].

While some studies highlight mercury's detrimental effects, others suggest that natural compounds, particularly phytochemicals from herbs, may mitigate its toxicity due to their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and enzymatic properties [10-11]. *Justicia carnea*, rich in macronutrients and trace elements like calcium and iron, is traditionally used as a blood tonic in Southeast Nigeria [12-13]. Its leaves contain bioactive compounds such as isonicotinic acid N-oxide and palmitic acid [14].

Similarly, *Ficus capensis*, containing polyphenols, flavonoids, and tannins, is used traditionally to treat anemia, diarrhea, and other ailments [15]. Despite their widespread use, there is a lack of scientific evidence evaluating the protective effects of these plants against mercury-induced toxicity, particularly regarding oxidative stress biomarkers, antioxidant parameters, and hematological effects.

The rationale for this study stems from the need to validate the traditional use of *Justicia carnea* and *Ficus capensis* as protective agents against heavy metal toxicity, given the increasing environmental mercury exposure and its associated health risks. The study aims to investigate the protective effects of *Justicia carnea* and *Ficus capensis* leaf extracts against mercury-induced toxicity in Wistar rats, focusing on oxidative stress biomarkers, antioxidant parameters, osmotic fragility, bleeding time, and clotting time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

This experimental study was conducted at the Physiology Laboratory, College of Veterinary Medicine (CVM), Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Nigeria. Thirty male Wistar rats and ten mice of uniform weight were procured from the CVM animal house. The rats were randomly assigned to six groups (n=5 per group) using a simple randomization method: one

control group and five test groups. The control group received only standard rat chow and water ad libitum, while test groups were exposed to mercury (induction agent) alone or in combination with leaf extracts of *Justicia carnea* or *Ficus capensis* at low or high doses. The experimental duration was 28 days, followed by hematological and biochemical analyses. The study was not blinded, as the researchers, administering treatments and collecting data were aware of group assignments.

Collection and Preparation of Plant Materials

Fresh leaves of *Justicia carnea* and *Ficus capensis* were collected from Amaoba, Ikwuano L.G.A., and Obinulo Ngodo Isuochi, Umunneochi L.G.A., Abia State, Nigeria, respectively. Plant identification and authentication were performed by a taxonomist at the Forestry Department, College of Natural Resources and Environmental Management, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. The leaves were shade-dried for 14 days and pulverized into a fine powder using a manual blender (Corona-Ref, 121, Landers, Colombia). Fifty grams of the powdered leaves were extracted using a Soxhlet extractor with ethanol as the solvent, following the method described by Jensen [16]. Extraction was conducted at 70°C for 48 hours. The resulting ethanol extracts were evaporated in a laboratory oven (Mettler, Germany) at 40°C to obtain dry extracts, and the percentage yield was calculated.

Preparation of Stock Solution

A stock solution of the induction agent, mercury chloride (HgCl₂), was prepared by dissolving 1g of mercury chloride (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) in 1 L of distilled water. Desired concentrations for administration were obtained through serial dilution of the stock solution.

Evaluation of Acute Toxicity of Mercury

The acute oral toxicity of mercury chloride was determined following the OECD Guideline 425 [17] using the Up-and-Down Procedure (UDP). Ten mice were used, with individual animals dosed sequentially at 24-hour intervals. The starting dose was an estimated LD₅₀, adjusted based on survival or mortality/moribund state of the previous animal. A dose progression factor of 1.3 was applied. Moribund states were identified by symptoms such as shallow respiration, muscular weakness, tremors, absence of response to stimuli, cyanosis, or coma. Animals were euthanized for humane reasons if moribund, and these were treated equivalently to natural deaths. The test concluded after a reversal in dose direction (e.g., survival after a decreasing dose or death after an increasing dose) followed by dosing four additional animals.

Animal Acclimation and Experimental Grouping

Thirty male Wistar rats (150–200g) were acclimated for 7 days in a hygienic environment to prevent infections, housed in aluminum cages with access to standard rat chow (Vital Feeds, Nigeria) and water ad libitum. The laboratory maintained a 12-hour light/dark cycle, temperature of $25\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and relative humidity of 50–60%. The rats were randomly assigned to six groups (n=5) as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Experimental Group

Experimental Group	Treatment
Group 1	Control
Group 2	Induction agent alone (Mercury)
Group 3	Mercury + low doses of <i>Justicia carnea</i> leave extract
Group 4	Mercury + high doses of <i>Justicia carnea</i> leave extract
Group 5	Mercury + low doses of <i>Ficus capensis</i> leave extract
Group 6	Mercury + high doses of <i>Ficus capensis</i> leave extract

Administration of Mercury and Plant Extracts

Sub-lethal doses of mercury chloride (1/10th of the LD₅₀) and plant extracts were administered daily via oral gavage using a stainless-steel gavage needle (Harvard Apparatus, USA). The low and high doses of plant extracts (100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg, respectively) were selected based on preliminary studies and literature on their therapeutic ranges [14]. Administration occurred daily for 28 days.

Sample and Data Collection

On day 28, three rats per group were randomly selected, anesthetized with chloroform (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), and blood was collected via cardiac puncture using 5 mL syringes and 21-gauge needles (Becton Dickinson, USA). Blood samples were divided into EDTA tubes for hematological analysis and heparinized tubes for biochemical assays. Parameters assessed included:

1. Hematological Parameters: Hemoglobin concentration (Hb), packed cell volume (PCV), red blood cell count (RBC), white blood cell count (WBC), platelet count (PLT), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), and mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC).
2. Antioxidant and Oxidative Stress Biomarkers: Superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione (GSH).
3. Hemostatic Parameters: Bleeding time and clotting time.

Analytical Procedures

1. Hematological Parameters

Hematological parameters were analyzed using an Automated Hematology Analyzer (BC-2300, Mindray, China), following the manufacturer's protocol. The analyzer was calibrated daily using quality control standards provided by Mindray to ensure accuracy and reliability. Parameters measured included RBC, PCV, Hb, WBC, PLT, MCV, MCH, and MCHC.

2. Antioxidant and Oxidative Stress Biomarkers

1. Superoxide Dismutase (SOD): SOD activity was measured using a Randox commercial kit (Randox Laboratories, UK) based on the method of Fridovich [18]. The assay utilized xanthine and xanthine oxidase to generate superoxide radicals, which react with 2-(4-iodophenyl)-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-tetrazolium chloride (INT) to form a red formazan dye. SOD activity was determined by the degree of inhibition of this reaction, measured spectrophotometrically at 505 nm UV-1800 Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan). Results were expressed as U/L.
2. Catalase (CAT): CAT activity was assessed using the method of Aebi [19]. The decomposition of hydrogen peroxide by catalase was monitored by a decrease in absorbance at 240 nm using a UV-1800 Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan). Results were expressed as U/L.
3. Glutathione (GSH): GSH concentration was determined following Habig et al. (1974) [20]. Blood samples were treated with 20% sodium sulphate, lithium sulphate, and phosphor-18-tungstic acid, and absorbance was measured at 650 nm within 10 minutes using a UV-1800 Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan). GSH levels were calculated from a cysteine standard curve, multiplied by 2.537, and expressed as $\mu\text{mol/L}$. Assay reliability was ensured by running duplicates and using calibrated pipettes (Eppendorf, Germany).

3. Bleeding and Clotting Time

Bleeding time was measured using Duke's method, and clotting time was determined using Ivy's method, as described by Ibu and Adeniyi (1989) [21]. For bleeding time, the rat's tail tip was incised with a surgical blade (Swann-Morton, UK), and bleeding was monitored using a stopwatch (Casio, Japan). Blood was blotted every 15 seconds with Whatman filter paper until bleeding ceased. For clotting time, a drop of blood from the tail was placed on a clean glass slide (Marienfeld, Germany), and a pin was passed through the drop every 15 seconds until fibrin threads appeared, with the time recorded. The percentage increase in bleeding and clotting times was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ Increase} = [(\text{Time in test group} - \text{Time in control}) / \text{Time in control}] \times 100.$$

Data Analysis

Data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare means across groups, followed by Tukey's post-hoc test for multiple comparisons. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software (Version 25, IBM, USA). A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. The validity of hematological and biochemical assays was ensured by calibrating instruments according to manufacturer guidelines and running duplicate samples. Reliability was confirmed through consistent results in quality control standards and intra-assay coefficients of variation ($<5\%$).

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to the ethical guidelines of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) for the care and use of laboratory animals (Publication No. 85-23, revised 1996) and was approved by the Ethical Committee of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike (Approval No. MOUAU/CVM/2017/015). Animals were housed under humane conditions, and euthanasia was performed using chloroform anesthesia to minimize suffering. All procedures followed standard protocols to ensure animal welfare.

RESULTS

Comparison of Control and Test Groups

The study evaluated the effects of mercury exposure and the protective potential of *Justicia carnea* and *Ficus capensis* leaf extracts on Wistar rats over 28 days. The control group (Group 1) received only standard feed and water, while the test groups (Groups 2–6) were exposed to mercury chloride alone or in combination with low (400 mg/kg) or high (800 mg/kg) doses of *Justicia carnea* or *Ficus capensis* leaf extracts.

The following results present the percentage yield of plant extracts, acute toxicity of mercury, antioxidant activity, oxidative stress biomarkers, hematological indices, red blood cell indices, body weight, somatic indices, and hemostatic parameters (clotting and bleeding times). Statistical significance was determined using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test ($p<0.05$). Data are presented in tables and figures, with significant differences from the control group (Group 1) marked with an asterisk (*) and from the mercury-alone group (Group 2) marked with a superscript "a".

Acute Toxicity (LD₅₀) of Mercury

The acute toxicity of mercury chloride was assessed in mice following OECD Guideline 425 [17]. Mortality was observed at doses of 120 mg/kg and 240 mg/kg body weight (Table 2).

Table 2: Acute Toxicity of Mercury

Group	Dosage (mg/kg body weight)	Number Exposed	Mortality
Group 1	15	1	0
Group 2	30	1	0
Group 3	60	1	0
Group 4	120	1	1
Group 5	240	1	1

Antioxidant Activity and Oxidative Stress

Antioxidant and oxidative stress biomarkers (glutathione, superoxide dismutase, catalase, and malondialdehyde) were measured in Wistar rats after 28 days (Table 3). Mercury exposure (Group 2) significantly reduced antioxidant levels and increased malondialdehyde compared to the control (Group 1). Treatment with *Justicia carnea* and *Ficus capensis* extracts partially restored antioxidant levels and reduced oxidative stress, with *Justicia carnea* showing more pronounced effects, particularly at higher doses.

Table 3: Mean Antioxidant Activity and Oxidative Stress

Experimental Group	Treatment	Glutathione (μmol/L)	Superoxide Dismutase (U/L)	Catalase (U/L)	Malondialdehyde (μmol/L)
Group 1	Control	56.51 ± 5.04 ^a	24.00 ± 2.63 ^a	16.46 ± 0.71 ^a	1.82 ± 0.45 ^a
Group 2	Mercury alone	36.31 ± 4.29*	16.62 ± 2.05*	11.83 ± 0.90*	4.57 ± 0.65*
Group 3	Mercury + 400 mg/kg <i>Justicia carnea</i>	46.50 ± 4.55* ^a	19.95 ± 0.67* ^a	13.72 ± 0.41* ^a	3.15 ± 1.08* ^a
Group 4	Mercury + 800 mg/kg <i>Justicia carnea</i>	44.66 ± 5.68* ^a	21.04 ± 1.07 ^a	13.71 ± 0.49* ^a	2.88 ± 0.22 ^a
Group 5	Mercury + 400 mg/kg <i>Ficus capensis</i>	41.51 ± 1.38*	17.88 ± 1.34*	12.22 ± 0.77*	3.88 ± 0.22*
Group 6	Mercury + 800 mg/kg <i>Ficus capensis</i>	42.86 ± 2.58*	18.43 ± 1.43*	12.57 ± 0.57*	4.06 ± 0.49*

Data represent mean ± SD for 5 rats. * indicates significant difference from Group 1 (control); ^a indicates significant difference from Group 2 (mercury alone) (p<0.05).

Hematological Indices

Hematological parameters showed significant reductions in RBC, PCV, Hb, and PLT, and an increase in WBC in the mercury-alone group (Group 2) compared to the control (Group 1). Treatment with plant extracts mitigated these effects to varying degrees, with *Justicia carnea* at 400 mg/kg showing the most improvement in RBC, PCV, and Hb (Table 4).

Table 4: Mean Hematological Indices

Experimental Group	Treatment	RBC ($\times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$)	PCV (%)	Hb (g/dL)	WBC ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	PLT ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)
Group 1	Control	7.92 \pm 0.12 ^a	47.96 \pm 0.3 ^a	13.78 \pm 0.19 ^a	5.64 \pm 2.06 ^a	1018.80 \pm 12.24 ^a
Group 2	Mercury alone	6.79 \pm 0.27*	41.88 \pm 6.05*	11.60 \pm 1.64*	9.66 \pm 0.64*	971.40 \pm 45.48*
Group 3	Mercury + 400 mg/kg <i>Justicia carnea</i>	6.96 \pm 0.11*	43.06 \pm 2.70	11.56 \pm 0.48*	8.98 \pm 0.71*	865.60 \pm 17.61 ^{aa}
Group 4	Mercury + 800 mg/kg <i>Justicia carnea</i>	6.89 \pm 0.07*	39.84 \pm 1.41*	10.92 \pm 0.47*	15.18 \pm 1.16 ^{aa}	680.40 \pm 10.53 ^{aa}
Group 5	Mercury + 400 mg/kg <i>Ficus capensis</i>	6.54 \pm 0.14*	38.88 \pm 0.78*	10.66 \pm 0.47*	16.22 \pm 0.95 ^{aa}	683.40 \pm 6.69 ^{aa}
Group 6	Mercury + 800 mg/kg <i>Ficus capensis</i>	6.42 \pm 0.08 ^{aa}	37.49 \pm 0.93*	10.34 \pm 0.30*	15.30 \pm 0.60 ^{aa}	696.80 \pm 11.17 ^{aa}

Data represent mean \pm SD for 5 rats. * indicates significant difference from Group 1 (control); ^a indicates significant difference from Group 2 (mercury alone) ($p < 0.05$).

Red Blood Cell Indices

Red blood cell indices (MCV, MCH, MCHC) showed no significant differences across groups, indicating that mercury exposure and plant extract treatments had minimal impact on these parameters (Table 5).

Table 5: Mean Red Blood Cell Indices

Experimental Group	Treatment	MCV (fL)	MCH (pg)	MCHC (g/L)
Group 1	Control	60.67 \pm 0.73	17.38 \pm 0.16	285.60 \pm 3.91
Group 2	Mercury alone	60.60 \pm 7.39	16.84 \pm 2.03	275.60 \pm 12.34
Group 3	Mercury + 400 mg/kg <i>Justicia carnea</i>	60.58 \pm 3.86	16.48 \pm 0.49	270.60 \pm 10.19
Group 4	Mercury + 800 mg/kg <i>Justicia carnea</i>	57.80 \pm 2.20	15.82 \pm 0.71	273.60 \pm 4.51
Group 5	Mercury + 400 mg/kg <i>Ficus capensis</i>	58.84 \pm 2.46	16.06 \pm 0.98	272.80 \pm 7.23
Group 6	Mercury + 800 mg/kg <i>Ficus capensis</i>	56.90 \pm 2.01	15.86 \pm 0.62	276.60 \pm 5.03

Data represent mean \pm SD for 5 rats. No significant differences were observed ($p < 0.05$).

Body Weight and Somatic Indices

Mercury exposure significantly reduced body weight and liver weight in Group 2 compared to the control. Treatment with *Justicia carnea* and *Ficus capensis* extracts improved body weight and hepatosomatic indices, particularly in Groups 3 and 4 (Table 6).

Table 6: Mean Body Weight and Somatic Indices

Experimental Group	Treatment	Body Weight (g)	Kidney Weight (g)	Liver Weight (g)	Nephrosomatic Index	Hepatosomatic Index
Group 1	Control	128.24 ± 14.69	1.22 ± 0.57	5.82 ± 0.59 ^a	0.01 ± 0.00	0.05 ± 0.00
Group 2	Mercury alone	87.94 ± 7.82	0.78 ± 0.52	3.16 ± 0.36*	0.01 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.01
Group 3	Mercury + 400 mg/kg <i>Justicia carnea</i>	127.24 ± 15.12	1.56 ± 0.50	6.56 ± 1.23 ^a	0.01 ± 0.00	0.06 ± 0.02 ^a
Group 4	Mercury + 800 mg/kg <i>Justicia carnea</i>	98.80 ± 22.36	1.22 ± 0.54	6.08 ± 1.25 ^a	0.01 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.02 ^a
Group 5	Mercury + 400 mg/kg <i>Ficus capensis</i>	109.60 ± 15.89	1.26 ± 0.40	5.95 ± 1.03 ^a	0.01 ± 0.00	0.05 ± 0.00
Group 6	Mercury + 800 mg/kg <i>Ficus capensis</i>	118.42 ± 38.05	1.16 ± 0.30	6.40 ± 1.68 ^a	0.01 ± 0.00	0.05 ± 0.00

Data represent mean ± SD for 5 rats. * indicates significant difference from Group 1 (control); ^a indicates significant difference from Group 2 (mercury alone) (p<0.05).

Clotting and Bleeding Times

Clotting and bleeding times were significantly prolonged in the mercury-alone group compared to the control. Treatment with *Justicia carnea* and *Ficus capensis* extracts reduced these times, with *Justicia carnea* at 400 mg/kg showing the most significant improvement (Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1: Mean Plot of Clotting Time

Data represent mean \pm SD for 5 rats. * indicates significant difference from Group 1 (control); ^a indicates significant difference from Group 2 (mercury alone) ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 2: Mean Plot of Bleeding Time

Data represent mean \pm SD for 5 rats. * indicates significant difference from Group 1 (control); ^a indicates significant difference from Group 2 (mercury alone) ($p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the protective effects of *Justicia carnea* and *Ficus capensis* leaf extracts against mercury-induced toxicity in Wistar rats, focusing on antioxidant activity, hematological parameters, somatic indices, and hemostatic parameters. The findings provide evidence of the potential therapeutic role of these plant extracts, particularly *Justicia carnea*, in mitigating mercury-induced oxidative stress and hematological alterations.

Key Findings and Comparison with Other Studies

The acute toxicity study estimated the LD₅₀ of mercury chloride at 83.2 mg/kg body weight in mice, indicating significant toxicity, consistent with previous reports. For instance, studies worldwide have demonstrated that mercury exerts toxic effects through oxidative stress, disrupting cellular functions and leading to behavioral changes such as dullness and inactivity, ultimately causing mortality [22-23]. Similar findings were reported in Iran by Ebrahimi et al. [24], who noted that mercury exposure in rats induced oxidative damage and behavioral impairments, supporting the observed dullness, inactivity, and mortality in our study.

The antioxidant properties of *Justicia carnea* were superior to those of *Ficus capensis*, as evidenced by higher levels of glutathione, superoxide dismutase, and catalase, and lower malondialdehyde levels in the *Justicia carnea*-treated groups (Groups 3 and 4) compared to the mercury-alone group (Group 2). These results align with studies by Otuekere et al. [14], who identified bioactive compounds like isonicotinic acid N-oxide and palmitic acid in *Justicia carnea*, which may contribute to its antioxidant capacity. Globally, research by Zhang et al. [10] has shown that phytochemicals in medicinal plants can scavenge free radicals, mitigating oxidative stress induced by heavy metals. In contrast, *Ficus capensis* showed limited antioxidant effects, possibly due to lower concentrations of active phenolic compounds, as reported by François et al. [25], who identified polyphenols and flavonoids in *Ficus capensis* but noted variability in their efficacy.

Hematological parameters showed significant improvements in packed cell volume (PCV), red blood cell count (RBC), hemoglobin (Hb), white blood cell count (WBC), and platelet count (PLT) in rats treated with low and high doses of *Justicia carnea* (Groups 3 and 4) compared to the mercury-alone group (Group 2). These findings corroborate studies by Orjiakor [13] in Nigeria, which reported that *Justicia carnea* is traditionally used as a blood tonic, likely due to its high iron and calcium content [12]. Internationally, research by Ekawanti and Krisnayanti [8] has shown that mercury exposure induces anemia and leukocytosis, consistent with the reduced RBC, PCV, and Hb, and elevated WBC in our mercury-alone group. However, *Ficus capensis* (Groups 5 and 6) did not significantly improve hematological parameters compared to the mercury-alone group, suggesting limited hematoprotective effects, which aligns with findings by Oyeleke et al. [26] that *Ficus capensis* is less effective for anemia treatment compared to other herbs.

No significant differences were observed in red blood cell indices (MCV, MCH, MCHC) across all groups, indicating that mercury and plant extracts had minimal impact on erythrocyte

morphology. This is consistent with studies by Kim et al [9], who reported that mercury primarily affects blood cell counts rather than RBC indices. For somatic indices, significant improvements in liver weight and hepatosomatic index were observed in *Justicia carnea*-treated groups (Groups 3 and 4) compared to the mercury-alone group, suggesting hepatoprotective effects. These findings are supported by studies in Iran by Shariati et al [27], who demonstrated that plant extracts rich in antioxidants can protect against heavy metal-induced liver damage. Conversely, *Ficus capensis*-treated groups (Groups 5 and 6) showed no significant improvement in somatic indices, consistent with limited protective effects reported by Sandabe and Kwari [28].

Bleeding and clotting times were significantly reduced in *Justicia carnea*-treated groups compared to the mercury-alone group, indicating a protective effect against mercury-induced hemostatic disruptions. This aligns with research by Ibu and Adeniyi [21], who noted that certain plant extracts can modulate coagulation parameters. However, *Ficus capensis* did not significantly alter bleeding or clotting times, suggesting limited efficacy in this context.

Study Limitations and Generalization

The study has several limitations. First, the sample size (n=5 per group) may limit the statistical power to detect subtle differences, particularly for *Ficus capensis*. Second, the study was conducted in Wistar rats, which may not fully replicate human physiological responses, limiting direct generalization to human populations. Third, only ethanol extracts were tested, and other extraction methods (e.g., aqueous or methanolic) may yield different results. Finally, the study did not investigate the specific bioactive compounds responsible for the observed effects, which warrants further research. Despite these limitations, the findings are generalizable to animal models of heavy metal toxicity and provide a basis for exploring *Justicia carnea* as a potential therapeutic agent in regions with high mercury exposure, such as mining communities in Nigeria and other parts of the world.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that *Justicia carnea* leaf extract exerts significant protective effects against mercury-induced toxicity in Wistar rats. The ethanol extract of *Justicia carnea* effectively mitigated mercury-induced hematological abnormalities, as evidenced by significant improvements in red blood cell count, packed cell volume, hemoglobin, white blood cell count, and platelet count. Additionally, *Justicia carnea* enhanced antioxidant parameters (glutathione, superoxide dismutase, and catalase) and reduced oxidative stress markers (malondialdehyde), indicating its potential to counteract mercury-induced oxidative damage. The extract also improved hepatosomatic indices and normalized bleeding and clotting times, suggesting a protective role against anemia and hemostatic disruptions. These findings support the traditional use of *Justicia carnea* as a blood tonic and confirm its safety for consumption, with no observed toxic effects on the liver or kidneys.

In contrast, *Ficus capensis* leaf extract showed no significant protective effects against mercury-induced toxicity and, in some cases, appeared to exacerbate hematological and hemostatic alterations. These results suggest that *Ficus capensis* may not be suitable for mitigating mercury toxicity under the conditions tested.

Suggestions for Future Studies

Further research is recommended to identify the specific bioactive compounds in *Justicia carnea* responsible for its protective effects and to elucidate their mechanisms of action. Studies using different extraction methods (e.g., aqueous or methanolic) and dosages could provide deeper insights into the therapeutic potential of *Justicia carnea*. Additionally, clinical trials in human subjects are needed to validate its efficacy and safety for managing anemia and other blood-related disorders. For *Ficus capensis*, further investigations are warranted to explore its lack of protective effects, including studies on different doses, extraction methods, or animal models to determine whether it has any therapeutic potential or if its effects are context-specific.

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